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Executive Summary

This document describes our refined recommendations for the BioExcel Training Programme.

The BioExcel Centre of Excellence (CoE) Training Programme has been developed using a competency-based training needs analysis; this method has been aligned with a number of other international projects as many of the challenges faced at this level of continued professional development are common across many domains. The competency-based approach makes the most of the expertise available within the BioExcel CoE, the detailed domain knowledge of the biomolecular simulation experts and the expertise in developing and running a successful training programme.

The current BioExcel Competency profile is presented comprising a total of 31 competencies: 5 Generic Competencies, 13 Scientific Competencies; 8 Generic Computing Competencies and 5 Parallel Computing Competencies. The competencies have been mapped against the learning outcomes of existing training resources (internal and external resources) and a gap analysis has been performed to reveal the highest training needs.

Recommendations are provided for user training based on the competency requirements of the BioExcel users. These users include:

(1) entry-level users (e.g. bench-based molecular life scientists with a very limited computational background, working in both academic and industrial settings). The training for this group will be primarily focussed on bridging the gap between life-science and HPC/HTC computing (users transitioning from a bench-based molecular life science background). The BioExcel summer school will address the training need in the generic computing competencies and a range of webinars are in preparation to assist users in gaining the necessary fundamental knowledge.

(2) Specialist users (e.g. structural bioinformaticians/computational chemists, medicinal chemists and others.). The training needs for this group will be quite specific for each use case (e.g. specific software packages, optimisation). Training will include basic and advanced training in the BioExcel codes (GROMACS, HADDOCK, CPMD) and other relevant scientific software (e.g. workflow systems).

(3) Systems Administrators & Applications Experts (e.g. computational service providers, including systems administrators, applications experts and others involved in providing high-end computational services and software to biomolecular scientists). The needs for this group are two-fold and will include improving the communication with the other user groups, as well as providing bespoke training for this group (likely via webinars and in collaborations with other initiatives), likely topics will include software installation.

The BioExcel Training Programme combines face-to-face events, webinars, virtual and online training.

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1 Introduction

This document reports on the outcome of our training needs analysis and summarises our plans for further training activities. This deliverable follows on from the initial results presented in D4.2: Competency framework, mapping to current training & initial training plan and the work carried out in Task 4.1.

When developing a comprehensive training programme, it is essential to gain a good understanding of your target audience; what is it that they need to do and where is the gap between what they can do now and what they would like to be able to do in future? And what training resources are already available, as resources are limited and should be used strategically?

An additional point to consider is that, though part of the people who provide training at this level of science are academics with specific teaching duties and therefore are experienced at teaching, there is a substantial group of trainers who are primarily software developers, biomolecular scientists or computer scientists rather than professional trainers; training is something they do above and beyond their regular occupation, and in most cases they have received no guidance on how to train. Many of the challenges faced by organisations needing to establish advanced training programmes or continued professional development initiatives are shared (e.g. limited resources, providing on-demand training, lack of time for continued development, trainer recognition); BioExcel CoE is actively collaborating with other training initiatives to improve the communication between trainers and training professionals so that these challenges can be addressed together rather than in isolation.

The approach BioExcel Centre of Excellence (CoE) has chosen to develop a training programme is to start from a competency-based training needs analysis. This approach makes the most of the expertise available within the BioExcel CoE, on the one hand the detailed domain knowledge of the biomolecular simulation experts of BioExcel and additionally the expertise in developing and running a successful training programme.

A competency is an observable ability of any professional, integrating multiple components such as knowledge, skills and behaviours.

The key aspects of the competency-based approach are:

- Competencies are observable, so acquisition can be validated objectively
- Evidence of competency can be collected in a competency portfolio
- Competencies are shared 'currency' applicable to learning of all types and at all career stages

A competency profile lists and defines all the competencies that an individual might need to fulfil a particular role, or that define specific user groups. Typically, competency profiles are defined by professional bodies or learned societies in collaboration with employers. The competency profile will not only be the basis of the BioExcel Training Programme but will inform the CoE as a whole of additional

user needs. The method for developing the competency profile and the mapping & Gap analysis described later in this document has been aligned with a number of other international projects (e.g. RItrain, CORBEL, LifeTrain).

Figure 1 illustrates the generic steps taken in developing a competency profile. It is important to note that this is an iterative process in which the profile is refined over time. To expedite the first two steps WP4 organised a workshop (3-4th May 2016: BioExcel: addressing training needs for advanced simulations in biomolecular research, EMBL-EBI, Hinxton) to gather input for the BioExcel competency profile.

Figure 1: Generic steps taken in development of a competency profile.

Deliverable 4.2 has outlined in great detail the development process of the BioExcel competency profile. In deliverable 4.3 we will only give a brief overview of this process in order to focus on presenting the final result and how, as a Centre of Excellence, we plan to use the profile to create a training programme that continues to respond to the highest priority needs of BioExcel's main user groups beyond the end of the CoE's pilot phase.

As illustrated in figures 2 and 3, an individual can possess a competency at different levels, and may develop that competency over time. We have formalised these competency levels with a scale that starts at no competency required in a specific area (N/A) increasing to Awareness and Working Knowledge, and culminating in Specialist Knowledge.

Figure 2: Levels of competency and their definition.

As individuals progress through their careers, their competency increases either through the acquisition of new competencies or by further developing previously gained competencies. Figure 3 illustrates a model developed by Rochelle Trachtenberg and collaborators, which divides this journey into three distinct phases. This model highlights the development process that biomolecular researchers (and other researchers) undergo throughout their careers. An Apprentice has the prerequisite knowledge needed but hasn't gained any experience of applying this knowledge in the workplace. A Journeyman has some experience of applying knowledge and is actively gaining further experience. The last stage of this career progression model is the Master, who has sufficient mastery of the role to be able to coach an apprentice to the level of a Journeyman.

Figure 3: Career progression model applied to gaining knowledge, this model was developed by Rochelle Trachtenberg, Georgetown University Medical Centre.

2 The BioExcel Competency Profile

2.1 Process for developing the BioExcel Training Programme

The process we used to develop the BioExcel Training Programme has four distinct phases as highlighted in figure 4. Phase 1 is defining the competencies needed to be able to exploit the products and services offered by BioExcel. In this phase we have focussed our attention on three user groups: Entry-level users, Expert users and computational service providers, such as systems administrators and applications experts. What drives these groups was defined in D4.2 but an extract is available in Appendix 1. As a Centre of Excellence we do not want to reinvent the wheel but focus our resources where they are most needed. Many high quality training resources are available through our project partners and other external resources. We have done a search for existing training resources in order to map our competencies against the learning outcomes of the existing resources (Phase 2) and conducted a gap analysis in order to reveal where the highest training needs are (Phase 3). Phase 4 of this process is developing and delivering training in these priority areas. It is important to note that this is an iterative process: feedback received by trainees, users and trainers will allow us to further refine the competency profile and ultimately deliver higher quality training.

Figure 4: Overview of the iterative process of developing the BioExcel Training Programme

2.2 The BioExcel Competency Profile version 1.0

Table 1 provides a full overview of the BioExcel Competency profile, comprising a total of 31 competencies; 5 Generic Competencies, 13 Scientific Competencies; 8 Generic Computing Competencies and 5 Parallel Computing Competencies. Each competency has been further broken down to define the knowledge, skills and behaviours that an individual would need to be considered competent in an area. Appendix 2 illustrates the levels of competency for each of the user groups according to the levels outlined in figure 2. This information has not been formally integrated in the current version of the competency profile because it is as yet incomplete. Due to the competencies being merged or separated after the initial training needs workshop there are gaps for some competencies while other reflect information for multiple competencies. Adding the required levels of competency to the profile will be addressed throughout the project when we interact with the different user groups at workshops, conferences and other events (including online).

Competencies	Knowledge	Skills	Behaviours
1. Generic Competencies			
1.1 Function effectively in teams to accomplish a common goal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding of the context of the persons in the team - Aware of cultural differences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication - Conflict management - Time management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invites two-way communication; actively listens/pays attention; able to excite participation and commitment from others - Delivers on his/her actions and inspires this behaviour in others - Informs others of relevant information appropriately and on time
1.2 Comprehend and comply with professional, ethical, legal, security, and social issues and responsibilities, and uphold these in the workplace as appropriate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broad understanding of the relevant ethical, legal, and social issues - Understanding of internal ethical and legal policies - Understanding of organisational responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can interpret the letter and spirit of policies (ethical, legal, etc.) - Applies risk management skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confronts or reports potentially unethical behaviour or behaviour at odds with the organisation's values - Complies with internal policies - Respects confidentiality
1.3 Communicate effectively with a range of audiences, technical and nonprofessional.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broad understanding of communication models - Can distinguish between different target audiences and identify the most appropriate means of reaching them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active listening skills - Appreciates the value of social media and uses it effectively to communicate effectively with different audiences - Able to work effectively with creative professionals (e.g. designers, animators, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicates clearly and precisely with people at all levels - Delivers points in a structured and logical manner - Seeks out openness from others; gives straightforward, candid

		<p>journalists</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to translate complex concepts to different audiences 	<p>opinions to all</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicates effectively even in difficult situations - Anticipates audience needs and tailors communications to the audience and the context
1.4 Engage in continuing professional development (CPD).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aware of organisational changes and external environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Face-to-face communication skills - Ability to objectively review own performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrates curiosity to learn new skills or knowledge outside current expertise - Prioritises and plans for CPD
1.5 Identification and understanding of user needs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broad understanding of scientific disciplines and its ecosystem - Recognises different types of user, their interests and motivation - Appreciates the importance of user experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to differentiate wants from needs - User requirements/needs collection - Expectations management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proactive in discovering different users and their motivation - Actively facilitates gathering of use cases and user requirements - Seeks out and acts on user feedback
2. Scientific Competencies			
2.1 Apply computing expertise appropriate to the discipline and level of expertise (software as well as hardware).	<p>Knowledge including but not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computer architecture - Essential Algorithms - Programming - Databases & data structure - Information security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluates software - Understands applicability, optimisation and scope of different tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Keeps up-to-date with knowledge domain

2.2 Apply expertise in formal & natural sciences appropriate to the discipline.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has a deep comprehension of biological problems - Comprehends that a biological theory is not necessarily true - Fundamental scientific knowledge (biology, chemistry, physics) - Mathematics and statistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has an interdisciplinary view - Asks relevant, well-defined biological questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Takes a comprehensive approach to problems - Consults with colleagues - Looks for prior work - Displays scientific humbleness (own and other results) - Allows for unexpected results
2.3 Detailed comprehension of the scientific process and an ability to apply it (e.g. experimental design; inclusion of controls; QA, QC, processing, visualisation and interpretation of results).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knows where to find help - Comprehends the need for positive and negative controls - Comprehends the need for replicates (and what type, how many etc.) - Comprehends the principle garbage in, garbage out (GIGO) (for example generic or custom parameters for molecular dynamics) - Has a deep understanding of his/her own data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formulates a hypothesis - Tests a hypothesis - Accurately judges the validity of his/her results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Asks for help and/or verification - Prepares before starting a new process
2.4 Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is aware of the different types of licensing - Understands the significance and potential ambiguity of licensing depending on where you work (academic/industry, funding etc.) - Understands the difference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chooses appropriate license for his/her own software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Always checks the license information for software - Questions ambiguity in license information - Checks software is licensed

	between open and closed licenses		
2.5 Use a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	- Knows where tools are available	- Chooses the right tool for the problem at hand	- Actively searches for available sources of support (training material, forum, helpdesk etc.)
2.6 Evaluate the ability of a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	- Has a deep comprehension of biological problems - Comprehend the capabilities and limitations of computer-based system, process, component and programs.	- Creative thinking & problem solving - Has an interdisciplinary view	- Keeps up-to-date with emerging techniques and applications
2.7 Comprehension of the local and global impact of high-performance computing (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) on individuals, organizations, and society.	- Understand what areas are impacted by HPC technologies	- Accurately judges added value of HPC technologies for different scenarios and user groups	- Disseminate the importance of HPC technologies
2.8 Comprehension of how data-driven science, data analysis and computational modelling can be combined to generate and test hypotheses (e.g. machine learning, data mining, pattern recognition).	- Understands that science is an iterative process - Comprehends that models require experimental validation	- Accurately judges the validity of his/her results	- Comprehends that results might be difficult to interpret
2.9 Identify and compile appropriate data sets to address specific research questions	- Has knowledge of different datasets - Is aware of the concept of unique identifiers	- Assesses data quality - Judges fit-for-purpose - Actively identifies new datasets - Tracks where data came	- Advertises the existence of good quality datasets to others - Contributes to public datasets when appropriate

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehends the need to question / validate data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> from - Combines data from different sources - Data preparation/clean up 	
2.10 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in data management / organization / archiving and storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knows and understands the data formats people are using - Is aware of the backup policy of the institution/compute resource - Ability to judge what data needs to be kept for storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrates knowledge of the file system structure - Tracks every step in a process (traceability) - Version control - Backup - Documentation - Automates data analyses where appropriate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Backs up his/her work in non-redundant ways - Documents his/her work - Has a version control system in place
2.11 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in distributed data management and data management planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehends the need for standards (including ontologies) - Understands the importance of metadata - Comprehends the challenge surrounding legacy data (e.g. inaccessibility, resourcing, IP) - When to move data, and when to run code elsewhere 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Annotates metadata (tools) - Uses ontologies - Structure data, where applicable submit to databases - Safely and efficiently moves data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses standards and ontologies - Looks for existing ontologies rather than create his/her own ontology - Captures sufficient metadata - Adds his/her data in supplementary information of journal articles (e.g. SMILES, InChI for compounds) - Actively promotes the use of standards, metadata annotation
2.12 Search for, read and assess literature / manual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehend the need for a literature review (anything 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessing quality (methods, results, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducts a literature review when appropriate

	<p>similar done? Data available?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is able to find relevant literature (different sources of) (e.g. PubMed, Europe PMC) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critically read scientific literature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Will look at sources of literature outside his/her comfort zone / discipline
<p>2.13 Presenting your results to community (writing papers, conference presentation, YouTube)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knows which forums exist to present scientific results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Write scientific journal paper - Write and present a conference talk - YouTube - Proficient at scientific poster design - Deep understanding of what to present and what not to present - Can target his/her presentation at the right audience / level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Judge the appropriate medium to present through
<p>3. Generic Computing Competencies</p>			
<p>3.1 Comprehension of, and compliance with, good programming practice (as promoted, for example, by www.software-carpentry.org).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehends the need for best practice - Is aware of where (or with whom) to find examples of or written guidelines on best practice in his/her field 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inspires others to adhere to best practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actively promotes best practice by leading by example - Will try and identify best practice in a relevant area
<p>3.2 Analyse a problem and identify and define the computing requirements appropriate to its solution (e.g., define algorithmic time and space complexities and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Know how to describe algorithmic performance and complexity (e.g. Big O notation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is able to benchmark a system to get an estimate of the required computing time - Identify bottleneck in the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Write documentation

hardware resources required to solve a problem).		system (network, CPU, RAM, etc.)	
3.3 Apply knowledge of the operating system.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficiently navigates his/her way around the Operation System (OS) - Is transitioning from Graphical User Interface (GUI) to command line (if not already proficient) - Demonstrates knowledge of the file system structure - Knows where to find the location of important configuration files & applications - Is aware of OS-related file format differences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creates and manages files and directories in a system using a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and using command line - Connects to remote systems with a GUI and the command line - Be able to use Unix/Linux features like pipes & redirection - Changes access permissions when required - Creates and manages files and directories in a system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When you can't do something, search for it on the web - Back-up files - Uses access permissions appropriately
3.4 Write/adapt computer programs (software development) for biomolecular simulations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognises common programming concepts like loops and function calls - Comprehends the pros and cons of different programming languages - Knowledge of existing code/libraries to re-use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adapt existing programs - Compile code - Run test - Recognises appropriate file types - Knows when quick and dirty is appropriate and when writing for reusability is appropriate - Program in an appropriate language - Writes portable code - Writes efficient code 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conform to best practices for writing reusable code - Uses revision control - Uses a text editor with support for programming

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Writes appropriate tests - Debug code 	
3.5 Write his/her own scripts to perform tasks in context of biomolecular research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge of existing command/libraries to reuse - Judges when a task should be automated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is able to automate the process of executing some processes remotely - Write & debug scripts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses appropriate scripting language
3.6 Install biomolecular simulation software on his/her computer.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knows where to download software & dependencies to install - Comprehend the difference between kinds of binaries & source - Awareness of different types of account (e.g. user, admin, etc.) and when they should be used - Deep understanding of his/her platform (hardware, OS version, ...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select appropriately packaged code - Be able to use package managers - Be able to revert a system to a known state 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reads the README - Checks licencing before installing/running software - Appreciates the impact of installing/running software on other users of the machine
3.7 Deploy and test non-commercial software, including software that is built collaboratively and on a volunteer basis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Git (repositories), GitHub, SVN, mercurial-versioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - debugging (Mission Control, VisualVM,..) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - work in collaborative fashion
3.8 Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems availability and optimisation, storage used; scheduling maintenance at appropriate times and communicating this to users).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remote administration tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linux/UNIX sysadmin commands - LSF commands - Recognise bottlenecks in the system (Network, CPU, RAM, etc.) - Forward planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actively consider the impact on the user

4. Parallel Computing Competencies			
4.1 Assess computational workflow systems and their potential benefits.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is aware that workflow systems exist and what they do - Comprehends the pros and cons of different workflow systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluates and selects an appropriate workflow system - Install workflow manager - Ability to run a workflow - Write and modify a workflow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seeks out and makes use of appropriate existing workflows and workflow components
4.2 Apply knowledge of batch system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understands what resources are required per job - Demonstrates knowledge of the concept of queues and the runtime environment - Know about versions of software that are installed - Can estimate who is responsible for observed issues (a hardware issue? a software issue? a user environment issue?) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Writes a good batch script making use of available batch system features 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reads the documentation - Ask the right person for help
4.3 Write computer programs that can run on a parallel computer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Git (repositories), GitHub, SVN, Mercurial-versioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Programs using an appropriate language/paradigm - Recognises (independent) units of work and potential parallelism (and any dependencies) - Uses appropriate tools to debug, profile, refactor parallel code 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reads the documentation

<p>4.4 Assess advantages and limitations for deploying, executing and optimising computations in a cloud/grid environment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluates the pros and cons of running computations in the cloud - Evaluates the pros and cons of using grid technologies - Demonstrates knowledge of container technologies (e.g. Docker) - Demonstrates knowledge of the concepts related to virtualisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Routinely undertakes a cost-benefit analysis to understand whether cloud resources are the best value - Able to package software/data and deploy to the cloud - Selects an appropriate grid/cloud provider - Can build and provision a Virtual Machine (VM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seeks out and makes use of appropriate existing Virtual Machines, etc.
<p>4.5 Apply knowledge of performance profiling to measure suitability of computing platforms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Know that there are tools to help measure performance - Know how your machine's architecture and hardware can affect the performance of your code 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be able to profile a code - Recognise bottlenecks in a code - Be able to refactor code in order to remove bottlenecks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Run codes using appropriate resources (number of processors, etc.)

Table 1: The BioExcel Competency Profile listing the competencies and the Knowledge, Skills and Behaviours needed to become competent. The levels of competency required by each user group is partially available in Appendix 2.

3 Mapping and Gap Analysis

Here we present the results of the mapping and gap analysis that was carried out.

3.1 Mapping

A total of 173 training resources were identified, 10 relevant training portals, 125 online training resources (mostly courses & tutorials) and 38 face-to-face courses (see figure 5). The search for relevant training resources was not meant to be a comprehensive overview of all available training resources (this would be hugely time consuming and likely impossible because much scientific training is done internally in the context of graduate training programmes or staff training) but was intended to provide us with a representative set of widely accessible training resources. We focused our search on online resources because we know, from our own experience as users of and trainers for computational resources that this type of training enables to learn when and where they need the training. Face-to-face events are often considered the gold-standard of training but if a prospective trainee is not accepted on a course or has just missed a course application deadline, online training resources that can be accessed at any time are invaluable.

Figure 5: Total number of identified training resources used for the mapping and gap analysis (excl. training portals), colour coded by type of resource. Grey = Training Portals, Blue = online, Orange = Face-to-Face

The learning outcomes of the identified online and face-to-face (link to full mapping in Appendix 4) resources have been mapped against the BioExcel competencies (figure 6 and 7).

Figure 6: Graphical overview of the mapping of available training resources to the BioExcel Competencies. The colours refer to the competence areas; purple = Generic Competencies, green = Scientific Competencies, pink = Generic Computing Competencies, blue = Parallel Computing Competencies

Figure 7: Mapping of available training resources to the BioExcel Competencies, colour coded based on whether the resources are online or face-to-face. Blue = online, Orange = Face-to-Face

As a rough guide, we set our threshold at five training resources. In other words, if there are fewer than five available training resources covering a competency, we consider it to be a high priority area for the development of new training. As expected, for some competencies (such as 2.2, apply expertise in natural sciences appropriate to the discipline), there are many relevant training resources available. For others (such as 2.4, Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy) there are very few training resources available.

3.2 Gap Analysis

A detailed gap analysis (tables 2 and 3) has been performed to provide additional insight into the results of the mapping exercise and to define an action plan to address the highest training needs.

Coverage	Insufficient training resources identified but outside BioExcel scope	BioExcel or External training resources identified. Note that coverage can be partial or fragmented and/or aimed at only a select user group.	Insufficient training resources identified
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Table 2: Key for the mapping and gap analysis

Table 3 provides a full overview of the competencies, how many resources have been mapped against it, a summary of the coverage of the mapping and any comments related to the scope of the competency or whether the identified resources are internal or external to the Centre of Excellence as well as the main training need or actions to be taken by BioExcel.

Competency (code and full description)	Courses Mapped	Coverage	Comments	Main training need or Actions to be taken by BioExcel
1.1 Function effectively in teams to accomplish a common goal.	1		Insufficient training resources identified but outside BioExcel scope	n/a
1.2 Comprehend and comply with professional, ethical, legal, security, and social issues and responsibilities, and uphold these in the workplace as appropriate.	1		Insufficient training resources identified but outside BioExcel scope	n/a
1.3 Communicate effectively with a range of audiences, technical and lay.	3		Insufficient training resources identified but outside BioExcel scope	n/a
1.4 Engage in continuing professional development.	1		Insufficient training resources identified but outside BioExcel scope	n/a
1.5 Identification and understanding of user needs.	5		Overlap with CORBEL	Could be addressed by BioExcel through building user profiles, case studies etc. rather than formal training as well as highlighting the competency-based approach as a success story (e.g. webinar, conference)
2.1 Apply computing expertise appropriate to the discipline and level of expertise (software as well as hardware).	15		Mainly external online resources	Scope for training webinars in collaboration with "Biomolecular Simulations for Entry Level Users" Interest Group
2.2 Apply expertise in natural sciences appropriate to the discipline.	34		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group. Highlighting specific courses suited to the BioExcel relevant domains would be beneficial.	Scope for training webinars in collaboration with "Biomolecular Simulations for Entry Level Users" Interest Group
2.3 Detailed comprehension of the scientific process and an ability to apply it (e.g. experimental design; inclusion of controls; QA, QC, processing, visualisation and interpretation of results).	18		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group. Not many courses take participants across the full scientific process. Biggest gap is controls, Quality Assessment (QA) and Quality Control (QC)	Highlight relevant courses. BioExcel should focus on QA/QC element and best practice

2.4 Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy.	3		Very high demand, also beyond BioExcel users	Needs actions coordinated across the CoE and ideally beyond. Clarification and unified strategy need to come before formal training
2.5 Use a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	12		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	BioExcel training available on specific resources, mainly online tutorials
2.6 Evaluate the ability of a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	11		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	BioExcel training available on specific resources, mainly online tutorials
2.7 Comprehension of the local and global impact of high-performance computing (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) on individuals, organizations, and society.	4		Unlikely the main topic of a training course but may be addressed in related courses	Could be addressed through a BioExcel Webinar or recorded Keynote lecture during a training course. Potentially also through written media (e.g. blog, review or journal paper).
2.8 Comprehension of how data-driven science, data analysis and computational modelling can be combined to generate and test hypotheses (e.g. machine learning, data mining, pattern recognition).	18		Mainly external online resources	Could be addressed through a BioExcel Webinar or recorded Keynote lecture during a training course. Potentially also through written media (e.g. blog, review or journal paper) expertise within the CoE will be sought (maybe overlap with BioExcel use cases?)
2.9 Identify and compile appropriate data sets to address specific research questions	12		Partial or fragmented coverage. Quality Assessment (QA) and Quality Control (QC) aspect lacking	Has an overlap with 2.3, BioExcel should focus on QA/QC and showcasing best practice with examples relevant to biomolecular modelling (e.g. models/structures)
2.10 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in data management / organization / archiving and storage	9		Mainly external resources	Search for collaboration with other initiatives to address the training needs for this competency (e.g. CORBEL, EDISON, ELIXIR, Software/Data Carpentry). Training within this topic does not fall within the core BioExcel expertise.

2.11 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in distributed data management and data management planning	1		Difficult to identify training resources specific to distributed data management, potentially an element within more generic data management resources.	Search for collaboration with other initiatives to address the training needs for this competency (e.g. CORBEL, EDISON, ELIXIR, Software/Data Carpentry). Training within this topic does not fall within the core BioExcel expertise.
2.12 Search for, read and assess literature / manual	5		Partial or fragmented coverage. Additional resources needed for critical assessment of literature	Highlight relevant courses but outside main BioExcel training scope
2.13 Presenting your results to community (writing papers, conference presentation, YouTube)	6		Mainly external online resources	Highlight relevant courses but outside main BioExcel training scope.
3.1 Comprehension of, and compliance with, good programming practice (as promoted, for example, by www.software-carpentry.org).	12		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	Coordinated action plan needed as users will likely need assistance across multiple competencies
3.2 Analyze a problem and identify and define the computing requirements appropriate to its solution (e.g., define algorithmic time and space complexities and hardware resources required to solve a problem).	6		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	
3.3 Apply knowledge of the operating system.	11		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	
3.4 Write/adapt computer programs (software development) for biomolecular simulations.	14		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	
3.5 Write his/her own scripts to perform tasks in context of biomolecular research.	6		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	
3.6 Install biomolecular simulation software on his/her computer.	1		Insufficient training resources identified	

3.7 Deploy and test non-commercial software, including software that is built collaboratively and on a volunteer basis.	8		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	
3.8 Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems availability and optimisation, storage used; scheduling maintenance at appropriate times and communicating this to users).	9		Partial or fragmented coverage, and/or aimed at only a select user group	
4.1 Assess computational workflow systems and their potential benefits.	10		Available resources are at intermediate to expert level, often only focussed on individual resources.	Liaise with the BioExcel Workflows and Pipelines IG
4.2 Apply knowledge of batch system	4		Available resources (PRACE/PATC) are at intermediate to expert level. Partial or fragmented coverage	Coordinated action plan needed as users will likely need assistance across multiple competencies
4.3 Write computer programs that can run on a parallel computer	16		Available resources (PRACE/PATC) are at intermediate to expert level. Partial or fragmented coverage	
4.4 Assess advantages and limitations for deploying, executing and optimising computations in a cloud/grid environment	16		Available resources (PRACE/PATC) are at intermediate to expert level. Partial or fragmented coverage	
4.5 Apply knowledge of performance profiling to measure suitability of computing platforms	15		Available resources (PRACE/PATC) are at intermediate to expert level. Partial or fragmented coverage	

Table 3: Overview of the mapping and gap analysis for the BioExcel competency profile. Explanation of the colour coding of the coverage is available in Table 2.

The following competencies are insufficiently covered (clustered by area):

1. Generic Competencies

1.5 Identification and understanding of user needs.

2. Scientific Competencies

2.4 Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy.

2.7 Comprehension of the local and global impact of high-performance computing (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) on individuals, organizations, and society.

2.11 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in distributed data management and data management planning.

3. Generic Computational Competencies

3.6 Install biomolecular simulation software on his/her computer.

4. Parallel Computing Competencies

4.2 Apply knowledge of batch system

However, in addition to this, the following competencies have been identified as having partial or fragmented coverage, and/or are aimed at only a select user group (competencies clustered by area):

2. Scientific Competencies

2.2 Apply expertise in natural sciences appropriate to the discipline

2.3 Detailed comprehension of the scientific process and an ability to apply it (e.g. experimental design; inclusion of controls; QA, QC, processing, visualisation and interpretation of results).

2.5 Use a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.

2.6 Evaluate the ability of a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.

2.9 Identify and compile appropriate data sets to address specific research questions

3. Generic Computational Competencies

3.1 Comprehension of, and compliance with, good programming practice (as promoted, for example, by www.software-carpentry.org).

3.2 Analyse a problem and identify and define the computing requirements appropriate to its solution (e.g., define algorithmic time and space complexities and hardware resources required to solve a problem).

3.3 Apply knowledge of the operating system.

3.4 Write/adapt computer programs (software development) for biomolecular simulations.

3.5 Write his/her own scripts to perform tasks in context of biomolecular research.

3.7 Deploy and test non-commercial software, including software that is built collaboratively and on a volunteer basis.

3.8 Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems availability and optimisation, storage used; scheduling maintenance at appropriate times and communicating this to users).

4. Parallel Computing Competencies

4.3 Write computer programs that can run on a parallel computer

4.4 Assess advantages and limitations for deploying, executing and optimising computations in a cloud/grid environment

4.5 Apply knowledge of performance profiling to measure suitability of computing platforms

3.3 Additional comments on the mapping and gap analysis

Mapping courses or training resources to competencies is a time consuming exercise with limited precision. As mentioned earlier in this document we do not aim to capture all available courses but we believe that is not a significant problem because we are looking for an overview, a representative snapshot of what is currently available to BioExcel's users. The mapping process is a balancing exercise between gaining a rapid overview of a training resource's coverage and learning outcomes (if available!) and accurately mapping a resource to the right competency. The mapping accuracy could be improved by either mapping to the Knowledge/Skills/Behaviours of a competency or doing a detailed analysis of each resource, which would require completing the course. Clearly the time required for this phase of the process would become unmanageable. Perhaps the most significant confounder is that, in many cases, an individual course or training resource only partially covers a competency. We have noted this in our gap analysis and, where possible, specified major gaps within that partial coverage. We believe that the approach we have taken is a reasonable balance between speed and accuracy.

As a point of best practice the BioExcel Centre of Excellence will add learning outcomes, relevant tags (the competencies & topic areas each resource maps to) and a description of the intended audience to all our new training material. We will gradually add these to historical training material as well. This will be implemented in phase 2 of the Knowledge Resource Center (see 4.2).

4 Recommendations for the BioExcel Training Programme

The section below will address how BioExcel plans to address the gaps in the competency mapping through the BioExcel Training Programme.

In an ideal world we would be able to address all gaps identified, but limited resources mean that it is necessary to prioritise. Priority is given to areas where the need is felt to be most urgent and where there is the best match between the training need and the expertise available in the CoE. We will continue to liaise with other international training initiatives to highlight the remaining training needs,

especially to other initiatives that may be better placed to address a specific need (e.g. Data management for EDISON, or User Experience for CORBEL).

Based on the competency profile and the gap analysis we plan to target the BioExcel training Programme at the following three user groups:

1. Entry-Level Users: We anticipate that the training need for this group will be primarily focussed on bridging the gap between life-science and HPC/HTC computing (users transitioning from a bench-based molecular life science background).

2. Specialist Users: the training needs for this group will likely be quite specific for each use case (e.g. specific software packages, optimisation). As an additional source of information we anticipate requesting input from the Interest Groups (IG) as to what the highest priority training needs are (through IG leaders & WP3).

3. Systems Administrators & Applications Experts: this group has a double aim, to enable the previous groups to be able to communicate better with the systems administrators as well as to provide training for this group directly. We anticipate that trying to engage this group in training could be challenging, webinars would be likely be the best option. Training of interest could be software installation webinars.

4.1 BioExcel Training Programme

4.1.1 New Face-to-face events

BioExcel CoE will organise a minimum of six training events during this funding cycle; on average this will be 2 events per year. It is important to note that outside of the planned BioExcel training events, most of the BioExcel partner additionally provides training of relevance to BioExcel's user constituency; for example, training on each of the three BioExcel codes is offered. The new BioExcel face-to-face events will be designed to address areas of unmet need, or areas where we can add considerable value by organising courses as BioExcel. The added value could be achieved by bringing together multiple resources or experts from distinct but complementary areas, and highlighting how they can work together.

Year	Date	Title
		Competencies
Year 1 Completed	3-4 th May 2016 (EMBL-EBI)	BioExcel: addressing training needs for advanced simulations in biomolecular research http://bioexcel.eu/events/workshop-addressing-training-needs-for-advanced-simulations-in-biomolecular-research/
Year 1 Completed	20-21st October 2016 (BSC)	BioExcel: workflow training for computational biomolecular research http://bioexcel.eu/events/bioexcel-workflow-training-for-computational-biomolecular-research/
		4.1

Year 2	10-13 April 2017 (KTH)	BioExcel – PRACE Spring School; Focus is on GROMACS and related codes, analysis and visualization tools https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/502/
		2.3, 2.5, 2.6
Year 2	3-7 th July 2017	Foundation skills for HPC in computational biomolecular research (project based) http://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/2017/foundation-skills-hpc-computational-biomolecular-research
		Generic Computing Competencies (3.1 – 3.8)
Year 3	TBC	Introduction to HPC computing for life scientists
		4.2 – 4.5 (building on from “Computational skills for life scientists”)
Year 3	TBC	Advanced face-to-face training on the three BioExcel codes HADDOCK, GROMACS, CPMD
		2.5; 2.6

Table 4: Planned BioExcel face-to-face events mapped to BioExcel competencies.

In addition to the full BioExcel courses, we anticipate BioExcel resources to be integrated in existing courses at the different BioExcel partners. For example, a session on docking using HADDOCK will be integrated into the EMBL-EBI Structural Bioinformatics course in 2017. We anticipate there being additional opportunities where BioExcel resources can provide additional value to existing courses, a full report will be provided in D4.5 (PM18).

4.1.2 Online & blended learning

To complement the face-to-face training, we will create the following online training resources.

- **Virtual Training:** Virtual training would combine the use of Virtual Machines (VMs), which participants can access remotely, and the BioExcel Webinar platform to establish 2-way communication (audio & video) with the participants. We are currently exploring the possibilities of running a pilot session (likely between March 2017 and October 2017) with the University of Utrecht, which would include a HADDOCK lecture and hands-on tutorial. If, after evaluation by the participants and organisers, this mode of delivering training is considered successful is could be expanded into a virtual autumn or winter school.
- **New online training content:** this will include the BioExcel webinars (all of which are delivered to a live audience but made available afterwards by video), online tutorials and any online training courses that will be produced. A number of online training resources are already available and accessible via the BioExcel website and will be added to the Knowledge Resource Center once operational; this includes the tutorial that are already available for the three codes and the external training resources identified during the mapping phase (also see appendix 4). The existing resources are mainly centred around BioExcel’s three major software packages (HADDOCK, GROMACS & CPMD). The exception is the EMBL-EBI

train online portal (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/>) which has a much wider remit.

- Workflow-based training:** Workflow-based training goes beyond an individual online training course because it allows us to build an online environment in which we tie together a range of online courses and training related resources that will contribute to deep learning over a longer period of time. Each workflow-based course will address a specific research problem: for example, during our competency workshop in May, our delegates defined a number of workflow-based use cases. The classic example is performing docking to create a shortlist of small molecules with bioactivity against a particular target macromolecule, followed by QM/MM to model the molecular dynamics of this interaction in more detail. A prerequisite to this kind of work is selecting an appropriate structural model from PDBe with which to do the remainder of the experiment. There are at least three different steps here, each requiring a training course. EMBL-EBI and ELIXIR have both devised systems for bringing together different courses into ‘metacourses’: EMBL-EBI has created the Bioinformatics For Discovery portal (Figure 8), which provides workflow-based ‘metacourses’ based on industrial applications; TeSS has created training ‘packages, which allow a set of individual training materials to be bundled together in a logical order. We will use one or both of these sets of infrastructure to create metacourses for BioExcel use cases.

The screenshot displays the EMBL-EBI Bioinformatics For Discovery training portal. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'EMBL-EBI', 'Services', 'Research', 'Training', and 'About us'. Below this, the main header reads 'Bioinformatics For Discovery' with a user icon and navigation links for 'Module workflows', 'Discussion area', 'My assessment results', 'My account', and 'Log out'. A progress indicator shows '1 You have completed 1 of 4 workflows'. A welcome message says 'Welcome back Vera EBI' and 'You're currently working on workflow "Exploring protein targets"'. Three workflow cards are listed: 'Bioinformatics principles' (Complete), 'Exploring protein targets' (In progress), and 'Chemical biology' (Currently locked). A sidebar on the right shows a checklist of sections in the current workflow: 'What's known about my protein?' (You are here), 'Is my protein an exploitable target?', 'Is there a known structure?', 'Are there any known chemical interactors?', 'What else is known?', and 'Chemical biology workflow assessment test'.

Figure 8: Screenshots of the EMBL-EBI workflow-based training portal. This page show three workflows, one has been completed (Bioinformatics principles), one is in progress (Exploring

protein targets) and one workflow is waiting to be unlocked (Chemical Biology). The side panel shows the different section in the Exploring protein target workflow.

Title or description	
Type	Competency
Assessing structure quality in the PDB archive (Speaker: Matthew Conroy, EMBL-EBI)	
Webinar – 8 th February 2017	2.3, 2.5
Where to get compute resources and the benefits and challenges of different types – Part one. Local Compute (Speaker: Lee Larcombe, ELIXIR-UK – Q1 2017)	
Webinar	3.2
Where to get compute resources and the benefits and challenges of different types – Part two. Cloud & HPC computing (Speaker: Steven Newhouse, EMBL-EBI – Q1 2017).	
Webinar	2.7, 3.2, 4.4
An entry level webinar(s) that introduces users to concepts underlying biomolecular simulations (e.g. docking, molecular dynamics, free energy calculations)	
Webinar	2.1, 2.2, 2.5
Short seminars with questions and documentation on how to install specific software packages/codes (own environment & cloud deployment)	
Webinar / written documentation	3.6, 3.7, 4.4
An Entry level course, potentially based on modules PIs currently teach, topics to include: docking, molecular dynamics, free energy calculations (in collaboration with webinars)	
Online course	2.1, 2.2, 2.5
Mathematical basis of different modelling approaches	
Webinar	2.2, 2.3, 2.5

Table 5: Planned online training resources* mapped to BioExcel competencies. *Subject to available resources.

4.2 The BioExcel Knowledge Resource Center

Discoverability of training in our field is a major issue. One area in which we can rapidly add value is by creating a Knowledge Resource Center of all the training resources that we gathered for the gap analysis, tagging them according to topic and competency, and providing links to the resources themselves or the course providers' websites. The BioExcel Resource Center will be made available from the BioExcel website. We will also investigate the feasibility of synchronising the content of the BioExcel Training Knowledge Resource Center with other relevant aggregators of training content, such as ELIXIR's TeSS and EMTRAIN's on-course database.

Setting up the Knowledge Resource Center has been more problematic than anticipated. We initially anticipated using a plugin for the BioExcel website but this turned out not to work as anticipated due the tags (e.g. competency 1.1, HPC, GROMACS) not being searchable in an easy and efficient manner.

Instead we have decided on a 2-stage implementation:

Phase 1: all training resources used in the gap analysis are available through an online link that allows users to filter the resources based on the competency and domain. New resources will be added to the list [PM14] on a continuous basis.

Link to temporary Knowledge Resource Center:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1R75b-HpHg0omN4FpdRLVNjpN0efmw5eGeSV5xA8xSIY/edit?usp=sharing>

Phase 2: A relational database will be used to store the training resources. We are planning to clone an existing content database that needs to be extended to include the concept of a competency profile and individual competencies. Tags for topic areas will be implemented using the EDAM ontology topics - <http://edamontology.org/> [Q1-Q2 2017].

4.3 Sustainability

An important aspect that needs to be considered is the sustainability of the training material we produce.

The following considerations and actions have been taken:

- Create sustainable training material
 - pre-emptive planning to reduce the risk of material becoming outdated.
 - Plan videos so they can be broken down into small segments
 - Regular review cycle and if needed update existing training material
- Make existing training (internal & external) material available (on the BioExcel website or through the Knowledge Resource Center)
- Maximise the use of limited training resources: where possible we will make training material from face-to-face events available in an online version to increase the number of users that can benefit from the effort that went into producing the material.

4.4 BioExcel Travel Grant

To make sure we provide equal opportunities to all, we have decided to offer a limited number of travel grants for each of our face-to-face events.

4.4.1 Guidelines for awarding BioExcel travel grants

The BioExcel travel grants are fixed-amount support grants (amount per day) to attend BioExcel training events.

There are a number of eligibility criteria for a BioExcel travel grant:

- BioExcel travel grants can only be used for BioExcel training events.
- The applicant must be a student or early career scientist from an academic institution.
- The applicant's research or primary activity has to be within the BioExcel CoE field of interest.
- The applicant must not have received travel funding from BioExcel in the past 12 months.
- The applicant's institute cannot be a partner in the BioExcel CoE.
- The maximum funding award is 120 EUR per day of the course/workshop
- Applications from individuals who are presenting at the meeting (if applicable) are looked on more favourably than those who are not presenting.

If an applicant is successful in obtaining a travel grant, they can seek reimbursement after the event (to a specific maximum). Reimbursement is processed by EMBL-EBI using the organisational procedure for visitor reimbursement. Additionally, the beneficiaries are asked to write a blog post (300-400 words, incl. 1 photo) after the training event, either about their experiences at the course, their research interests (in layman's terms) or a relevant scientific topic. The blog is published on the BioExcel website and publicised via social media.

The blog posts from the first set of travel grant beneficiaries is already available on the website (<http://bioexcel.eu/hear-from-our-travel-grant-beneficiaries>).

4.4.2 Recipients of the BioExcel Travel Grant

Event	Dates	Last Name	First Name	Company Name
BioExcel: workflow training for computational biomolecular research	20-21/10/2016	Camacho Cano	Esther	Centro de Biología Molecular Severo Ochoa
BioExcel: workflow training for computational biomolecular research	20-21/10/2016	Flores	Antonio	Universidad de Málaga
BioExcel: workflow training for computational biomolecular research	20-21/10/2016	Hernandes Coutinho*	Felipe *	Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro *
BioExcel: workflow training for computational biomolecular research	20-21/10/2016	Matsoukas	Minos	University of Patras

BioExcel: workflow training for computational biomolecular research	20-21/10/2016	Gurinova	Jana	University of Vienna
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Table 6: List of recipients of a BioExcel Travel Grant. *Due to unforeseen circumstances this person needed to cancel their participation in the training event and subsequently the grant was withdrawn.

4.5 Link to consultancy

This section of the Training Programme is still a work in progress but there are several ways that we anticipate working with the BioExcel consultancy service (WP3). In many instances we anticipate a tiered system, where part of the training is available open and free of charge (WP4 organised training) but additional options are available through the consultancy services:

Expected consultancy modes:

- **Installation guides and services:** As mentioned in table 5, basic installation webinars (incl. Q&A) with accompanied written documentation are planned as part of the training programme. If users need additional help they will be able to receive this help via the BioExcel consultancy service.
- **Bespoke on-site training:** The main BioExcel courses are free to attend and all online material will remain openly available. However, if a group or organisation would like bespoke training at their site this could be arranged as part of the consultancy services. For example, a certain university requests a 2-day course on HADDOCK and GROMACS with a hands-on for their researchers.
- **Competency profile consultancy:** assistance could be provided in how to develop, implement and use a competency profile. This could include the running of a face-to-face events similar to the BioExcel training needs workshop in May 2016.

Additional consultancy modes that are possible but need further discussion:

- Individual advice on continued professional development based on the BioExcel competency profile. This type of advice could be combined with existing events such as training courses or conferences. The idea would be that a BioExcel user rates him or herself on the BioExcel competencies (awareness, working knowledge, specialist knowledge). Advice could be given as to which competencies (and specifically which knowledge, skills and behaviours) should be developed further if the user want to develop their him or herself along a specific path (e.g. system administrator in a HPC facility or software developer on a major biomolecular simulations package).

4.6 Measuring Impact & Risk

The following Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been identified to evaluate the BioExcel Training Programme:

ID	KPI	Justification	Reachable target	Stretch target	PM12
WP4_KPI01	Scope of available training material	Training material needs to cover sufficiently the available functionality of the software	80% of newly developed functionality within the project or older but popular one, based on user feedback and IG input	100% + additional as requested by the community	n/a, to be reported at PM18
WP4_KPI02	Number of CoE training events	Training events need to cover the main areas of expertise in the centre	2 per year, 6 in total	8 in total	2
WP4_KPI03	Number of people who have attended BioExcel courses	Courses need to cover topics of interest for the users	80% of maximum number of places	100% of maximum places	78% (63% event 1, 93% event 2)
WP4_KPI04	Course feedback	Rating of the training course based on the participant course feedback survey	> 60% responses "Good" or "Excellent" (based on 30 - 50 % response rate for survey filled in at the event)	> 80% responses "Good" or "Excellent" (based on 30 - 50 % response rate for survey filled in at the event)	97.7%
WP4_KPI05	Long-term impact, measured through post-6 month survey	Has the training received made the user more effective in their day-to-day activities e.g.	> 60% responses "Useful" or "Very Useful" for day-to-day activities (based on 15% - 25%	> 80% responses "Useful" or "Very Useful" (based on 15% - 25% response rate)	N/A

		have they gained a higher level of competence	response rate)		
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Table 7: Key Performance Indicators (KPI) developed to evaluate the BioExcel Training Programme. Data is provided for month 12 of the project.

Table 7 provides the KPIs that have been developed to evaluate the BioExcel Training Programme. WP4_KPI01 will be monitored after the two project releases (PM17 & PM36). WP4_KPI02 is at the level of the reachable target while WP4_KPI03 is just below the reachable target due to the low attendance of the first BioExcel training event (63%). The low attendance risk is reflected in table 8, R16. It is reassuring to see that the second event has a very high attendance rate (93%), the main way to mitigate low attendance in future events will be to make sure that registration is open far in advance, ideally 6 months before the event and promotion is started at the same time or even earlier. The course feedback for both events was very good, 97.7% of the people who responded found the event good or excellent. No long-term feedback assessment has been carried out to date (6 months' post event 1 is PM13), we anticipate reporting on this KPI from PM15. No other risks have been reported at PM12.

The following risks relevant to the BioExcel Training Programme have been identified:

Risk #	Description	Likelihood	Impact	Risk score (Likelihood x Impact)	Proposed Mitigation actions
Risks for the project execution					
R15	Failing to deliver project results and training to relevant audience	2	4	8	Training activities will be closely aligned with those of related initiatives such as CECAM, PRACE PATCs, EGI, EMBL-EBI, Elixir/Instruct etc. Further, the quarterly internal reports will allow tight monitoring of the progress and allow to take early action when required.
R16	Low numbers of delegates at training events or workshops	3	5	15	Effective promotion of events beginning several months before the event. Ideally registration should be open 6 months in advance with promotion of the event starting earlier or at the same time. Developing training that is specifically aimed towards filling perceived (and real) gaps in training
R17	Lack of involvement of other partners/WPs in Training (WP4)	3	4	12	WP4 is liaising with the other partners and WPs to make sure that training events are planned when sufficient resources are available. Events will be planned over a 6-months timeframe. External trainers will be brought in when needed
Risks for the long-term success of the CoE					
R30	Insufficient level of engagement with related national/international initiatives	3	3	9	Outreach and promotion with potential collaborators will be done via direct communication rather than using mass-market approaches such as mailing lists. Such personalised engagement is expected to nurture long-term interactions and create opportunities for more projects and high ROI. Training Interest Group will encourage engagement and collaboration.

Table 8: Risks and mitigating actions identified as relevant to the BioExcel Training Programme.

5 Training Interest Group

To aid collaboration with other training professionals we have started a Training Interest Group within BioExcel; the Interest Group (IG) could include trainers of specific resources (e.g. HADDOCK, GROMACS, CPMD etc.), training coordinators but is also a way to reach out to related external projects (e.g. other CoEs). As previously described in this document many of the challenges faced by organisations needing to establish advanced training programmes or continued professional development (CPD) initiatives are shared (e.g. limited resources, providing on-demand training, lack of time for CPD, trainer recognition). The Training Interest Group is the channel through which BioExcel collaborates with other training initiatives so that these challenges can be addressed together rather than in isolation.

The Training Interest Group was established with the following goals:

- Improve visibility of training initiatives and individual courses/resources. Members of the Training IG will be able to act as liaisons to other training initiatives including the other Centres of Excellence funded through the same call as BioExcel.
- Facilitate collaboration between projects to promote best practice and efficient use of resources and addresses common challenges.
- Improve communication between “computational trainers” and “life science trainers”.
- Promote the importance of high quality training

The Training IG is for those people responsible for or who have an interest in training within their institute or project or are a training professional (trainer, coordinator, lecturer) in a life sciences and/or computational field.

We anticipate webinars to be an important element of the Training Interest Group because they are accessible, since no travel is required and they can be watched after the event if people cannot attend on the day, they are relatively easy and inexpensive to organise.

The first webinar was held on the 23rd of November 2016 and titled “Defining training requirements for biomolecular researchers with high computational needs”. The webinar was used to officially launch the Training Interest Group. 18 people registered and 13 people attended on the day, the overall rating of the webinar was 4/5. The next webinar is currently being organised (Q1 2017), speakers have been identified but not invited yet. Working title is “Engaging the hard to engage – how to get life scientists/medics to embrace HPC/HTC”.

Face-to-face events around the following topics or external events are being considered:

- TBD (May. 2017): Using Dockers and VMs in training

- ECCB/ISCB competency workshop - BioExcel use case
- Lifelong learning Conference (EMBL Conference), 5th Dec 2017
- Best practice in virtual training (TBC)

A number of metrics have been defined by WP3 to rate the healthiness of an Interest Group. In addition to these metrics we will rate the healthiness of the Training IG by how connected the group is to other relevant initiatives; we anticipate visualising this information using a network graph.

6 Next steps

Prepare publication about using a competency-based approach to design a training programme (Q1 2017). Related to the publication, it will be important to find a visually appealing way of presenting the BioExcel competency profile. How will users be able to interact with the competency profile (Q1-Q2 2017).

We will deliver BioExcel training event 3 (Q2 2017; PM18) and BioExcel training event 4 (Q3 2017; PM21) during the second year of the project. Both events under development. We will implement phase 2 of the knowledge Resource Center – the timescale will be dependent on the EMBL-EBI web development team.

The next deliverable due on the BioExcel Training Programme D4.5 (PM18): Training report and updated plan. This document will report on the status of the generated training material, its usage and recommendation for its further improvements. The document will also contain evaluation of the completed training activities and recommendations for future ones.

7 Appendix

Appendix 1: Extract from D4.2 defining the user groups

In preparation of the workshop the decision was made to use Entry Level Users, Specialist Users and Systems Administrators and Application Experts as the initial target user groups. They will be part of the stereotypes and roles that will be used to define the service portfolio of the centre. The following profiles highlight what motivates these user groups.

Entry-level users:

An example might be a discovery biologist who wants to find potential interaction partners for a new target, or perhaps wants to see whether a library of small molecules could disrupt a potentially toxic protein-protein interaction. Potentially such a researcher might never have used modelling software before.

For this group, we need to deal with their 'unknown unknowns'; we wouldn't, for example, expect a discovery biologist to know how to tune a massively parallel computational problem to make it run efficiently. However, if we can teach them how to find out whether or not something is running efficiently, and who they need to talk to in order to solve this problem, we would already be solving a major source of frustration.

Specialist users:

They are modelling and simulation experts who want to do advanced and large scale modelling and simulations (for example, a computational chemist might want to run a huge chemical library past the entire PDB to find potential targets); perhaps they are using their cluster at the university and are eating up all the compute time; they might be looking for ways to fine tune their experiments, or to move them into a more computationally powerful environment (e.g. PRACE or EGI). The specifics of how these people optimise their simulations is specific to the application that they are using.

Systems Administrators and Application Experts (abbreviated to Systems Administrators):

Finally, we have the compute experts providing HPC services. They benefit from understanding enough biology to make sense of what their users want to do and why they want to do it; they need to understand how to optimise their compute architecture for the types of computational problems that biologists face (e.g. traditional high performance computing is not appropriate in situations where calculations are data-bound rather than cpu-bound. Data storage and management are crucial. Specific calculations depend on efficient input/output. Transmitting large data sets across a network may be problematic. Typically, the calculation is brought to the data, rather than the other way round.).

Appendix 2: Level of competency for the three user groups, Entry level user, Specialist user and System Administrators and Application Experts.

Note that the table below reflects our current best estimate for the competency level needed by the individual user groups. Due to the competencies being merged or separated after the initial training needs workshop there are gaps for some competencies. The competency survey described in D4.2 did not yield sufficient number of results for each of the user groups to provide sufficient resolution. Level of competency - A for awareness; WK for working knowledge; S for specialist knowledge; X for not relevant

Competencies	Entry Level Users	Specialist users	System Administrators and Application Experts
1. Generic Competencies			
1.1 Function effectively in teams to accomplish a common goal.			2W
1.2 Comprehend and comply with professional, ethical, legal, security, and social issues and responsibilities, and uphold these in the workplace as appropriate.			2W
1.3 Communicate effectively with a range of audiences, technical and nonprofessional.			1W 1S
1.4 Engage in continuing professional development (CPD).			2S
1.5 Identification and understanding of user needs.			
2. Scientific Competencies			
2.1 Apply computing expertise appropriate to the discipline and level of expertise (software as well as hardware).	3A 9W	4W 5S	2S
2.2 Apply expertise in formal & natural sciences appropriate to the discipline.	11W 2S	2W 10S	2A
2.3 Detailed comprehension of the scientific process and an ability to apply it (e.g. experimental design; inclusion of controls; QA, QC, processing, visualisation and interpretation of results).	3A 10W	2W 11S	1W 1S

2.4 Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy.	A-W	W	2S
2.5 Use a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	2A 10W	6W 8S (or 5W and 7S)	2S
2.6 Evaluate the ability of a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	7A 6W	7W 6S	2S
2.7 Comprehension of the local and global impact of high-performance computing (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) on individuals, organizations, and society.	3X 10A	9A 3W	1X 1S
2.8 Comprehension of how data-driven science, data analysis and computational modelling can be combined to generate and test hypotheses (e.g. machine learning, data mining, pattern recognition).	6A 7W	9W 5S	2A
2.9 Identify and compile appropriate data sets to address specific research questions	6A 7W 1S	8W 5S	2A
2.10 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in data management / organization / archiving and storage	3A 11W	1A 8W 5S	2S
2.11 Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in distributed data management and data management planning	11A 3W	12W 2S	2S
2.12 Search for, read and assess literature / manual	14W	8W 6S	1A 1S
2.13 Presenting your results to community (writing papers, conference presentation, YouTube)			1A 1W
3. Generic Computing Competencies			
3.1 Comprehension of, and compliance with, good programming practice (as promoted, for example, by www.software-carpentry.org).	10A 2W	1A 10W 1S	1W 1S

3.2 Analyze a problem and identify and define the computing requirements appropriate to its solution (e.g., define algorithmic time and space complexities and hardware resources required to solve a problem).	10A 3W	9W 3S	2S
3.3 Apply knowledge of the operating system.	14W	14S	2S
3.4 Write/adapt computer programs (software development) for biomolecular simulations.	12A 1W	13W	1W 1S
3.5 Write his/her own scripts to perform tasks in context of biomolecular research.	14W	5W 9S	2S
3.6 Install biomolecular simulation software on his/her computer.	12A 2W	14W	2S
3.7 Deploy and test non-commercial software, including software that is built collaboratively and on a volunteer basis.			
3.8 Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems availability and optimisation, storage used; scheduling maintenance at appropriate times and communicating this to users).			
4. Parallel Computing Competencies			
4.1 Assess computational workflow systems and their potential benefits.	14A	4A 7W	2S
4.2 Apply knowledge of batch system			2S
4.3 Write computer programs that can run on a parallel computer	7X 4A	7A 3W	1W 1S
4.4 Assess advantages and limitations for deploying, executing and optimising computations in a cloud/grid environment	2X 11A	11A 2W	2S
4.5 Apply knowledge of performance profiling to measure suitability of computing platforms	4X 8A	5A 7W	2S

Appendix 3: Recommended Training Portals

Name	URL	Domain	BioExcel Partner
Train online - repository of free online training courses on EMBL-EBI and collaborating data resources	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/	Bioinformatics	EMBL-EBI
OnCourse	https://www.on-course.eu/	Biomedical Science	EMBL-EBI
TeSS - ELIXIR's Training Portal	http://elixir-uk.org/training-platform	Life Science	External (EMBL-EBI)
Goblet - Training portal	http://mygoblet.org/training-portal	Bioinformatics	External (EMBL-EBI)
Find CPD	http://www.findcpd.com/	All	External (EMBL-EBI)
Coursera	https://www.coursera.org/	All	External (EMBL-EBI)
BioExcel Webinar Series	http://bioexcel.eu/category/webinar/	Biomolecular Research	KTH
PRACE Training Portal (Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe)	https://www.youtube.com/user/PRACECourses/featured	Advanced Computing	External (EMBL-EBI)
Archer	http://www.archer.ac.uk/training/virtual/	HPC	EPCC
Udacity	https://www.udacity.com/	Primarily computer science	External (EMBL-EBI)

Appendix 4: Existing training resources used for the mapping of training resources to BioExcel Competencies.

All training resources used for the gap analysis are available via the following link:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1R75b-HpHg0omN4FpdRLVNjpN0efmw5eGeSV5xA8xSIY/edit?usp=sharing>